

EFFECT OF GREEN LEAF ON VOLUME AND QUALITY OF BLACK TEA

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Abstract

Tea is one of the most popular beverages globally and majority of our produced tea is black tea. This study is conducted in Black Tea Factory of Bangladesh Tea Research Institute with three different leaf quality (GL_{80%}, GL_{50%}, GL_{30%}) to assess the difference of made tea volume and made tea quality due to different green leaf quality. The volume of made tea varies with the green leaf quality. Tea volume of individual each grade (FBOP, BOP, GBOP, OF and Dust) was lowest in GL_{80%} while highest in GL_{30%} leaf quality. Total polyphenols (16.23%), theaflavin (0.89%), brightness (27.77%) and caffeine (3.17%) found highest in green leaf with 80% good leaf. A fundamental quality criterion for determining the body, color, strength, brightness, and briskness of black tea beverage is the TF/TR ratio. Best ratio of TF:TR (1:10.39) was found in green leaf with 80% while the low quality of made tea with 1:12.47 ratio was found in low quality of green leaf (30% good leaf). Strongest positive relation (0.93^{***}) was found between total polyphenols and good leaf percentage. Correlation Coefficient (r) were +0.88^{***} and +0.80^{***}, respectively for caffeine and organoleptic score against good leaf (%) also explaining the presence of strong positive relationship between them. It can be concluded that, the volume and the quality, both biochemical and organoleptic of made tea mostly depends on the green leaf quality.

Keywords: Tea, Good leaf (%), Volume, Biochemical properties, Organoleptic quality

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Introduction

Tea is one of the most popular beverages globally consumed (Cheng, 2004; Vinson, 2000) with a per capita intake of around 120 ml per day (Mckay & Blumberg, 2002). It is mostly grown in China, Japan, India, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka as well as other many countries (Fatima & Rizvi, 2011). About 20% of tea is produced as green tea, while 80% of the nearly 2.5 million metric tons of produced teas are black teas and majority of consumed tea is black tea and green tea (Boehm et al., 2009). ITC (2021) estimates that global production, retention, imports and consumption of tea were 6,269 million kg, 4,444 million kg, 1,735 million kg, and 5,879 million kg, respectively in 2020. Since 1854, Bangladesh has been cultivating tea commercially with the establishment of country's first tea estate, the 'Malnicherra Tea Estate' in Sylhet. In 1947, there were only 28,734 hectares of tea cultivated area with a yield of 656 kg per hectare. By contrast, in 2020, there were 62,168.46 hectares of tea cultivation with a yield of 1561 kg per hectare (BTB, 2021). In 2020, there are 86,394 million kg of tea production in total, of which 79 million kg are CTC tea, 7 million kg are orthodox tea, and almost 1% are green tea (ITC, 2021).

There are four major separate steps in the production of black tea: withering, rolling or maceration, fermentation, and drying (Tomlins & Mashingaidze, 1997). Green leaf quality is an important criterion which is responsible for made tea quality. When first two leaves and the bud are plucked is generally termed as 'fine plucking', while 'coarse plucking' standard is called when three or four leaves and the bud are plucked (Wright, 2005). The optimal leaf quality compromise between yield and quality is thought to be two leaves and a bud (Banerjee, 1992). However, planters sometimes compromise with leaf quality by plucking comparatively less soft and younger shoots for extra production in a cropping year (Okinda & Bowa, 2012). But coarse plucking standard reduces made tea quality. For the development of flavored precipitates during the infusion process, the caffeine concentration of tea has a high correlation with its quality (Smith et al., 1993). The amounts of substances like amino acids, and catechins, as well as other substances like thearubigins and theaflavins, also significantly influence the sensory properties of tea (Kato et al., 2008). The sensory

qualities of tea, particularly the brightness of the tea color, have been reported to be influenced by thearubigins and theaflavins (Owuor & Obanda, 2001). It has been observed that made tea density changes through the year although the manufacturing processes remain more or less the same (Jose, 1999). This study is conducted to assess the difference of made tea volume and made tea quality due to different green leaf quality.

Materials and Methods

This experiment was carried out at Black Tea Factory of Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) Sreemangal, Moulvibazar from March 2022 to December 2022. Three categories of green tea leaves, (i) containing 80% good (fine) leaf (GL_{80%}), (ii) containing 50% good (fine) leaf (GL_{50%}) and (iii) containing 30% good (fine) leaf (GL_{30%}) of BTRI released clonal tea variety BT2 were the different treatments of the experiment. After the arrival of the green tea leaves into the factory, leaf analysis was immediately carried out to determine the good (fine) leaf percentage. The 'Ballometric method' was followed for assessing the good leaf percentage of the green tea leaves. In brief, fresh tea shoots were picked up at random and weighed to equivalent weight of 100 numbers of metal balls of equal size. Then the soft tender leaves (two leaves and a bud, soft single banji), which can be easily separated by slight hand pressure from the remaining portion of the shoots are separated manually and kept as good or fine leaves. When all the fine leaves were separated, the good leaves were weighed to equivalent weight against the same sized balls. At this time, the number of balls equivalent of the good leaf weight represent the good leaf percentage. For the manufacturing of black tea, BTRI standard manufacturing technique was followed which is Green Leaves→ Withering→ Rolling→ Oxidation→ Drying→ Sorting. In this experiment, made tea samples were sorted by FBOP, BOP, GBOP, OF and Dust grades according to standard mesh sizes. Made tea of each grade (FBOP, BOP, GBOP, OF and Dust) from three different green leaf quality (GL_{80%}, GL_{50%}, GL_{30%}) were used for volume measurement. After volume measurement, each grade from different green leaf quality were used for biochemical assessment. Total Polyphenols (%), Theaflavin (%), Thearubigin (%), TF:TR ratio, Total Color (%), Brightness (%) and Caffeine (%) of each sample were determined by following methods:

Method for Total Polyphenols (PL) determination (ISO 1402-1, 2005; Anesini et al., 2008)

In short, a test tube was filled with 1 ml of diluted sample. Then 5 ml of 10% Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent (FCR) and 4 ml of sodium carbonate solution (7.5% w/v) was added. Then this mixture in test tube was allowed to stand for 60 minutes at room temperature. After this period, absorbance was measured at 765 nm by using UV-vis spectrophotometer. Galic acid was used as standard. Using a standard curve for gallic acid, the total amount of polyphenols was represented as a percentage of mass on a dry matter basis for the sample.

Method for Theaflavin, Thearubigin, Total Color and Brightness (Borse, 2012)

Theaflavin (TF), Thearubigin (TR), Total Color and Brightness were estimated from tea brew by following the UV-vis spectrophotometric method with slide modification. A 9 g sample of tea was boiled in 375 ml of water for ten minutes. After that, a cotton cloth was used to filter the tea infusion. Infusion was kept at room temperature to cool it down. Disodium hydrogen phosphate 1% (w/v) aqueous solution was added to 6 ml of the infusion. 10 ml of ethyl acetate was added to that mixture by rapidly repeating inversion for one minute. The ethyl acetate layer containing the TF fraction was obtained after the bottom layer was drained away. Then, 5 ml of ethyl acetate was used to dilute the TF fraction. Absorbance measurements at 380 nm and 460 nm were used to determine the optical densities (E1, E2, and E3). To generate 25 ml of methanol (E1), 10 ml of TF extract was diluted. A 1 ml of infusion was diluted to ten ml with water and made up to 25 ml with methanol (E2). A 1 ml of tea infusion was mixed with 1 ml of 10% (w/v) of oxalic acid and diluted to 10 ml with water, the made up to 25 ml with methanol (E3). Optical densities of E1, E2 and E3 were measured at 380 nm and 460 nm. At 380 nm, the percent of TF and TR was computed, and at 460 nm, the percent of total color and brightness were calculated.

TF (%) = 2.25 X E1;

TR (%) = 7.06 X (4 E3 - E1);

Total colour (%) = 6.25X 4E2;

Brightness (%) = E1 /4E2 X 100;

Method for caffeine determination

The caffeine content in black tea was by following Belay et al. (2008) method with slide modification. 200 ml of water and 2.5 g of black tea sample were boiled for ten minutes while being stirred. It was then cooled at room temperature after filtering through cotton wool. With distilled water, this solution's volume was increased to 250 ml. Dichloromethane was added to this diluted mixture in a ratio of 1:1 in order to extract the caffeine using a separating funnel. With 25 ml of dichloromethane added to each round, the operation was carried out four times, and the solution were collected in a volumetric flask. The absorbance of the extracted solution was measured at 270 nm using a UV-vis spectrophotometer. By using a standard calibration curve, the caffeine (%) was calculated.

Organoleptic Quality assessment (BTRI, 2009; BTRI, 2021)

The traditional organoleptic tasting procedure was used to evaluate the organoleptic quality of manufactured teas and scoring was done on the basis of liquor characteristics. In order to make the liquor, boiling water was poured into a mug with a 142 ml (0.25 pint) capacity which contained 2.5 g of tea. The liquor was then poured into a bowl after 5 minutes of brewing as well as the infused leaf had to be taken from the mug into the inverted lid, which was then placed on top of the mug. Both the infused leaf and the liquor were then tasted by taster panel. Infused leaf appearance and liquor characteristics were assessed by scoring numerically out of 50 points as below:

- Infusion (10)
- Liquor characteristics (40 points): Liquor colour (10 points), Briskness (10 points), Strength (10 points), Creaming down (10 points)

The Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to compare means after the analysis of variance was calculated. The degree of relationship was measured using the correlation coefficient (r) by RStudio version 2022.07.2 and linear regression graph was prepared by using Microsoft Office Excel version 2019.

Results and Discussion

Effect of green leaf quality on made tea volume and quality (biochemical properties and organoleptic quality) were described below:

Effect of green leaf quality on made tea volume

It was observed that, in case of any particular grade, the volume differs with the green leaf quality. From Table 1 it was observed, tea volume of individual each grade was lowest in GL_{80%} while highest in GL_{30%} leaf quality. The density of tea is inversely correlated with volume, meaning that the density is higher when the volume is smaller and vice versa. In this experiment, made tea became more flaky or lighter with the decrease of green leaf quality. Flaky means lower density or high-volume tea which is subjected to problems in packaging and transportation because it covers more volume (area). On the other hand, grainy or low volume tea was made from higher quality green leaf which had more density and quality. The correlation coefficient (r) was (-) 0.99 explaining as a strong negative correlation between green leaf quality and made tea volume and the linear regression graph was made (Figure 1) where regression equation was $y = -0.2115x + 277.09$.

Table 1. Volume (cc) of 100 gm different graded tea from different leaf quality.

Green leaf quality (Good leaf %)	Volume (cc) per 100 gm				
	FBOP	BOP	GBOP	OF	Dust
GL _{80%}	297.56c	282.97c	265.29c	255.47c	200.74c
GL _{50%}	303.24b	288.18b	271.47b	259.37b	207.39b
GL _{30%}	308.39a	293.64a	275.39a	264.89a	213.19a
P value	0.046	0.022	0.031	0.026	0.011
CV (%)	7.45	8.28	6.36	8.61	7.84
LSD at 5% level of significance	4.17	5.04	2.94	3.97	5.81

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Fig. 1. Linear regression graph of y= Volume cc/100 gm against x= Good Leaf (%).

Effect of green leaf quality on quality of made tea

Quality of made tea is defined by both biochemical properties and organoleptic quality of made tea. Effect of green leaf quality on biochemical properties and organoleptic quality are described below:

Biochemical properties of made tea

With an increase of coarse plucking standards; the caffeine, theaflavin, total ash, and total water soluble solids contents of black tea decreased, although thearubigins (Amiri & Asil, 2007), crude fiber (Śmiechowska & Dmowski, 2006) and floride (Lu et al., 2004) content was found to be increased. Green leaf quality i.e. the 'Good leaf (%)' affects the biochemical properties of made tea (Table 2 and Table 3). From Table 3 it was observed that total polyphenols (PL), theaflavin (TF), thearubigin (TR), brightness (BR) and caffeine (CF) percentage were found to be decreased significantly with the decrease of good leaf percentage. The PL (16.23 %), TF (0.89 %), BR (27.77 %) and CF (3.17 %) found highest in green leaf with 80% good leaf. There was no significant change in TC. Since the concentrations of TF and TR are important quality indicators, the appropriate ratio between them is crucial to achieving the right balance of the black tea liquor's briskness, strength, brightness, body and color (Rahman et al., 2020). Gill et al. (2011) reported that the standard ratio of TF:TR is 1:10. In this study, the ratio of TF:TR was found to be increased with the decrease of good leaf percentage. Best ratio of TF:TR (1:10.39) was found in green leaf with 80% while the low quality of made tea with 1:12.47 ratio was found in low quality of green leaf (30% good leaf). Due to the fact that coarse plucking is attributed for the higher polyphenol oxidase level in mature shoots, a coarse plucking standard produced very high TR concentrations and low TF value (Teshome, 2019).

Table 2. Biochemical properties of different graded tea from different leaf quality.

Name of the tea grades	Green leaf quality (Good leaf %)	Total Polyphenol (%)	Theaflavin (%)	Thearubigin (%)	TF:TR	Total Color (%)	Brightness (%)	Caffeine (%)
FBOP	GL _{80%}	15.41	0.91	10.07	1:11.06	4.03	24.69	3.46
	GL _{50%}	12.94	0.73	8.64	1:11.83	3.53	23.31	2.69
	GL _{30%}	9.40	0.9	8.06	1:8.95	3.15	21.36	2.43
BOP	GL _{80%}	17.91	0.81	8.2	1:10.12	4.35	26.66	3.32
	GL _{50%}	14.76	0.83	9.14	1:11.01	4.1	23.13	2.83
	GL _{30%}	10.27	0.7	9.01	1:12.87	3.78	22.87	2.67
GBOP	GL _{80%}	16.73	0.92	9.5	1:10.32	5.23	33.73	3.27
	GL _{50%}	14.13	0.93	10.46	1:11.24	5	27.44	2.75
	GL _{30%}	10.15	0.7	9.53	1:13.61	4.85	24.13	2.48
OF	GL _{80%}	16.59	1.23	12.84	1:10.43	4.93	26.65	2.95
	GL _{50%}	13.99	0.94	11.98	1:12.74	4.38	24.14	2.72
	GL _{30%}	10.11	0.91	12.55	1:13.79	3.98	18.75	2.39
Dust	GL _{80%}	14.54	0.56	5.66	1:10.10	4.08	27.14	2.87
	GL _{50%}	13.42	0.93	9.66	1:10.38	3.85	22.89	2.56
	GL _{30%}	9.5	0.69	9.49	1:13.75	3.75	19.84	2.29

Table 3. Biochemical properties of tea from different leaf quality.

Green leaf quality (Good leaf %)	Total Polyphenol (%)	Theaflavin (%)	Thearubigin (%)	TF:TR	Total Color (%)	Brightness (%)	Caffeine (%)
GL _{80%}	16.23 a	0.89 a	9.25 c	1:10.39 c	4.52	27.77 a	3.17 a
GL _{50%}	13.84 b	0.87 a	9.98 a	1:11.47 b	4.17	24.18 b	2.71 b
GL _{30%}	9.88 c	0.78 b	9.73 b	1:12.47 a	3.9	21.39 c	2.45 c
P value	0.0001	0.045	0.0405	0.006	0.523	0.0075	0.0001
CV (%)	6.62	9.23	8.24	7.51	6.56	10.63	6.34
LSD at 5% level of significance	1.21	0.02	0.09	0.82	Ns	1.64	0.11

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Organoleptic quality of made tea

Organoleptic quality of tea also differs with the quality of green leaf (Table 4). Highest quality (32.892) made tea was found from GL_{80%} leaf quality while lowest quality (32.182) was observed in GL_{30%} leaf quality. Intermediate quality (32.570) made tea was found in GL_{50%} leaf quality.

Table 4. Organoleptic quality of tea from different leaf quality.

Green leaf quality (Good leaf %)	Infusion	Liquor colour	Briskness	Strength	Creaming down	Total
GL _{80%}	7.340a	7.604a	7.480a	7.432a	3.036a	32.892a
GL _{50%}	7.310b	7.504b	7.444b	7.380b	2.932b	32.570b
GL _{30%}	7.298c	7.330c	7.328c	7.338c	2.888c	32.182c
P value	0.0097	0.048	0.0036	0.0041	0.007	0.0068
CV (%)	3.94	4.87	2.39	3.18	3.72	2.63
LSD at 5% level of significance	0.004	0.09	0.003	0.04	0.009	0.18

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Organoleptic quality of made tea varies due to more good leaf percentage which possesses more biochemical compounds. As the good leaf percentage decreases, biochemical compounds also decrease with the overall liquor quality. The amount of reaction substrates (catechins) and enzymes (polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase) in fresh tea leaves is a key factor influencing the production of theaflavins. These elements also impact the made tea beverage's sensory quality (Mizani et al., 2011). With two leaves and a bud, the theaflavins (TFs) concentration was at its highest. But, lower amounts of polyphenols and polyphenol oxidase activity likely contributed to the decrease in TFs levels produced by additional leaves (Tüfekci & Güner, 1997). According to the age of the leaves, there are differences in the catechin distribution within a shoot (Robertson, 1983). Lin et al. (1996) reported that, higher amount of total catechins was found in the soft leaves (5.86%) while concentration was found to be declined in old leaves (2.15%) and stem (0.85%).

Relationship between biochemical properties with organoleptic quality of made tea and green leaf quality

Black tea's quality decreased regarding both of the plain and aroma quality characteristics with the decrease of plucking standards (Mahanta, 1988). Relationship between biochemical properties with organoleptic quality of made tea and green leaf quality was determined by Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r) value. From Figure 2, it was observed that strongest positive relation (0.93^{***}) was found between total polyphenols (%) and good leaf (%). Correlation Coefficient (r) were +0.88^{***} and +0.80^{***}, respectively for caffeine and organoleptic score against good leaf (%) also explaining the presence of strong positive relationship. The relation between total color and good leaf percentage

was insignificant where brightness had moderate relation (+0.75**). Negative but significant relationship was observed between TF: TR ratio and good leaf percentage. Significant strong relation also found between total polyphenols and caffeine content (+0.87***) as well as between total polyphenols and organoleptic score (+0.86***).

Fig. 2. Relationship between quality of made tea and green leaf quality.

Linear regression graph of Total Polyphenols (%), TF:TR ratio, Total Color (%), Brightness (%), Caffeine (%) and Organoleptic score against good leaf (%) was presented in Figure 3-8. Linear regression graph of Total Polyphenols (%), TF:TR ratio, Total Color (%), Brightness (%), Caffeine (%) and Organoleptic score were $y = 0.1172x + 6.3321$, $y = -0.0412x + 13.638$, $y = 0.0123x + 3.5384$, $y = 0.127x + 17.675$, $y = 0.0144x + 2.0074$, $y = 0.0139x + 31.804$ respectively.

Fig. 3. Linear regression graph of Total Polyphenols (%) against x= good leaf (%)

Fig. 4. Linear regression graph of TF:TR against x= good leaf (%)

Fig. 5. Linear regression graph of Total Color (%) against x= good leaf (%)

Fig. 6. Linear regression graph of Brightness (%) against x= good leaf (%)

Fig. 7. Linear regression graph of Caffeine (%) against x= good leaf (%)

Fig. 8. Linear regression graph of Organoleptic score against x= good leaf (%)

The findings were explained by the fact that tender and soft tea shoots have significant quantities of polyphenols, which causes the simple quality criteria of the made tea (Owuor & Obanda, 1995). When the more mature leaves of the tea shoots are utilized as the raw material for manufacturing, the quality of black tea is significantly reduced (Teshome, 2019).

Conclusion

The volume of made tea varies with the green leaf quality. Tea volume of individual each grade (FBOP, BOP, GBOP, OF and Dust) was lowest in GL_{80%} while highest in GL_{30%} leaf quality. Volume is inversely proportional to the density of tea i.e. larger volumes have lower densities, whereas smaller volumes have higher densities. Total polyphenols (%), theaflavin (%), thearubigin (%), brightness (%) and caffeine (%) were found to be decreased significantly with the decrease of good leaf percentage. Total polyphenols (16.23 %), theaflavin (0.89 %), brightness (27.77 %) and caffeine (3.17 %) found highest in green leaf with 80% good leaf. A fundamental quality criterion for determining the body, color, strength, brightness, and briskness of black tea beverage is the TF/TR ratio. Best TF/TR ratio (1:10.39) was found in green leaf with 80% while the low quality of made tea with 1:12.47 ratio was found in low quality of green leaf (30% good leaf). Strongest positive relation (0.93^{***}) was found between total polyphenols (%) and good leaf (%). Finally, it can be concluded that, the made tea quality i.e. both biochemical properties and organoleptic quality mostly depends on the green leaf quality. The quality of the tea is increased in accordance to the quality of the green leaf. So, our planters must put special consider on good quality green leaf to make best quality and high density made tea as well as to get more auction price.

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